

Semiosis as problem solving, problem solving as semiosis: modeling cognitive processes through Peirce's 10 classes of signs

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Abstract: This paper reconceptualizes problem-solving tasks as semiotic processes through C.S. Peirce's extended classification of signs (developed post-1903). We propose modeling semiosis itself as problem-solving, generalizing this concept to encompass all activities requiring habitualization of sign-action. Our approach establishes a synchronic functional anatomy of constraints based on Peirce's ten sign-classes — conceptualized as interdependent processes rather than discrete entities or stages. This view enables two reinterpretations: (1) The 10 sign-classes as constitutive components of problem-solving dynamics. (2) Ballat's diagram as a map of regional relationships between constraints, jointly applied to theorizing semiosis-as-problem-solving.

Key-words: problem-solving, semiosis, 10 classes of signs, C.S.Peirce.

1. Introduction

We solve problems all the time throughout our lives. Problem-solving tasks are not just puzzles, such as the Tower of Hanoi, or wayfinding challenges, such as navigating the underground system. Creating and interpreting artworks, doing science and politics, and running businesses can all be conceptualized as a series of complex and interlocked problem-solving tasks. Peirce's theory of inquiry (see Bertilsson, 2009; Hookway, 1985; Apel, 1981) can be conceptualized as having the form of problem-solving — the initial state is one of doubt, the goal state is of belief, and the intermediate states are achieved by different kinds of inferential steps. In this article, we model semioses as problem-solving tasks. In doing that, we generalize the notion of a problem-solving task to include all sorts of activities that require habitualization of sign action. To develop this, we examined and detailed C.S. Peirce's 10 classes of signs, a classification developed from 1903 onwards. It's important to note that there is still nothing resembling a semiotic theory of problem-solving in Cognitive Science or even in Cognitive Semiotics.

In other publications, we have stated that the consequence of developing new classifications is a significant increase in the accuracy of describing the possible relations between sign, object, and interpretant, expressed in terms of trichotomies (Queiroz, 2012a, 2012b). As we will detail in Section 3, these trichotomies are aspects according to which the S–O–I relation can be observed. This paper offers two original treatments of Peirce's 10 classes: their interpretation as components of problem-solving processes and an interpretation of Michel Balat's diagrammatic modeling of these classes in terms of regions and their relationships, which we apply here to the issue of semiosis as problem solving.

2. Triad (sign, object, interpretant) and categories in problem solving

The first step in modeling semiosis as problem-solving is to speculatively identify the fundamental terms and notions of semiosis (sign, object, interpretant; firstness, secondness, thirdness) in problem-solving tasks. We characterize problem solving as a process involving artifacts, problems, and solutions as co-dependent participants of a triadic relation-in-action (sign, object, interpretant). An implication is that we differentiate three levels or dimensions involved in the activity of problem solving — the artifact (sign, or S), the artifact in relation

to the problem (sign-object, or S-O), the solution as the mediator of the relation between artifact and problem (sign-object-interpretant, or S-O-I). An important distinction between our semiotic approach here and more traditional problem-solving models is that we don't postulate subsequent phases or stages in problem-solving, such as framing a problem and then searching the problem space (see Newell & Simon, 1972). We model problem-solving as a hierarchical interaction between levels — at the level of firstness, problem-solving is a process concerning the nature of artifacts; at the level of secondness, it is a process concerning the nature of the relationship between artifacts and the problems they embody; at the level of thirdness, it is a process concerning the nature of the interpretation of this relationship (between artifacts and problems). Following the triadic irreducibility of Peirce's model, our approach suggests operational irreducibility between the problem, the artifact, and the solution process.¹ There is no problem dissociated from artifacts and from a solution process, and vice-versa. This is in line with situated problem solving (Kirsh, 2009), and its central idea that artifacts not only “refer to” an abstractly formulated problem, but actually embody the problem for an agent-in-action.

Problem solving is a triadic process involving three indissociable elements — an artifact (1), which represents a problem (2), so as to allow for a solution (3). This triadic frame carries the premises and implications of Peirce's category system: firstness is associated with qualitative possibilities and with the sign, secondness is associated with reactive effects and with the object, and thirdness is associated with habitual regularity and with the interpretant.² Respectively, solving a problem involves three levels in a hierarchical process of semiosis, which we explore in the following paragraphs — framing a qualitative problem by means of artifact qualities (1), searching through a reactive problem by means of actual artifact states (2), habitualizing the solution to a regular problem by means of artifact habits (3).³ These are not necessarily subsequent steps in chronological order. “Framing” and “searching” here should not be understood in the sense of subsequent steps, as is most commonly the case in problem-solving theory — first one represents a problem and then one searches a problem space. In our framework, based on Peirce's hierarchical understanding of relations within relations, their ordering reflects a logical presupposition — the third level involves the second, the second involves the first, and the first has some degree of autonomy. Thus, in

¹ This property follows the formal principle of irreducibility of the triadic relation that characterizes semiosis (S-O-I relation). The irreducibility of semiosis can be understood as the non-deducibility of the behavior of the logical-functional elements of a triad from their behavior in simpler relations (Queiroz and El-Hani, 2006). Semiosis is a triadic logical relation, that is, a relation that irreducibly involves 3 sides: a first element, which has qualities in itself (monadic, or first relation), but which stands to a second element (dyadic, or relation of a relation), only so far as the dyadic connection between them is mediated by a third element (triadic relation). This is a recursive application of the categories: a semiotic relation is a phaneroscopic thirdness (S-O-I triad), and as such it involves a secondness (S-O dyad) and a firstness (S monad). sign, object and interpretant are irreducible terms of a semiotic relation (CP 5.484, EP 2:171).

² From the 1870s and 1880s onward, the categories came to describe irreducible types of relations—monadic, dyadic, and triadic—each serving a distinct and necessary unifying function by which objects are made intelligible (see Hausman, 1993: 109). Instead of deriving the categories from the analysis of sign relations, as he had done in “On a New List of Categories” (W 2: 49), Peirce presents them directly as three classes of relation: monadic, dyadic, and triadic (“One, Two, Three: Fundamental Categories of Thought and of Nature”, W 5: 242). This approach offers the advantage of generality, as all possible logical relations, including the sign relation, fall within one of these three classes.

³ “Framing” has multiple meanings, broadly relating to how something is presented or constructed. It can refer to the way information is presented, influencing how it's perceived (like in communication or decision-making). It also describes the physical act of constructing something, like in carpentry or photography. Additionally, it can mean falsely implicating someone in a crime.

practice, there is no such a thing as, for instance, an action of pure searching after one is done with framing. Framing is involved in searching, and habitualizing is instantiated in searching.

The first level of sign action (firstness of problem solving) is mainly dependent on the qualities of the artifact. The problem, at this level, can be characterized as qualitative because it is iconically determined by the artifact (the problem as represented by the physical and perceptual qualities of the artifact alone). The solution process, at this level, can be characterized as framing. To be framed is to be qualified, characterized, presented, or constructed in a certain way. The artifact has the capacity to frame a problem by giving it a material body and providing the conditions so that manipulation of the artifact allows solution of the problem. Framing a problem involves setting up a task environment, recruiting material resources from the environment and arranging them in specific ways (Kirsh, 2009). The term artifact, here, may also include body parts and movements of the agents involved. The core of this operation is the engagement and manipulation of physical and perceptual qualities of artifacts (qualisigns) so as to qualify a problem (endow it with qualities), the qualitative problem (which is an icon) that hypothetically allows for a solution (framing, which is a rheme).⁴ This level of sign action has a certain degree of autonomy and independence, in the sense that explorations in the artifact may actually transform the nature of the problem and the nature of the solution so that one may explore artifacts for their own sake, not guided by a theoretical understanding of a problem, but actually seeking for hypothetical ways to externalize a problem, that is, iconically determine a problem.

The second level of sign action — secondness of problem solving — is mainly dependent on the action/reaction process between the artifact being manipulated and the constraints of the problem. By reaction of the problem, we mean the capacity of the problem to act back at the artifact that embodies it, compelling the artifact to assume some configurations instead of others, thus bringing the problem-solving from the realm of possibilities to the realm of existents. The notion of a reactive problem involves realizing in practice (actualizing) tentative links between problem states and artifact states, especially the goal or final state, so that solving the problem becomes a matter of manipulating the artifact so as to achieve the goal state in the artifact. The solution process at this level corresponds to searching the problem space through how it reacts with artifact states. Here we are dealing with actual existent states of the artifact (sinsigns) rather than qualities considered in itself. This is a manipulation compelled by the necessities of a reactive problem (index), which realizes in actuality the solution process (dicent). (We will detail each of these classes in the next section.) The solution process, at this level, can be characterized as searching. Searching has a dicentic, or proposition-like, logical structure, in which artifact states are taken to be predicates of the current state of a problem.

The third level of sign action — thirdness of problem-solving — concentrates on the solution, and can be referred to as habitualization. A fully solved problem is one in which the solution is not only reached, but generalized for all habitual cases, that is, theoretically formalized (symbols), and understood (argument), so that the problem may always be solved under similar circumstances. This operation amounts to generalizing, from the situated task environment at hand, to any representation that frames that problem under similar conditions (legisign).

⁴ See, for example, the notion of manipulative abduction (Magnani, 2001).

3. Trichotomies and ten sign classes

Besides his best-known division of signs into icons, indexes, and symbols, Peirce developed other classifications. The classifications were developed at various moments, from 1867 to 1908, and are organized into what can be considered systems of classes: 3 classes, 10 classes, 28 classes, and 66 classes of signs (Borges, 2020; Queiroz & Stjernfelt, 2019; Farias & Queiroz, 2017, 2014). A division of signs into 10 classes is extensively described in his 1903 Syllabus (MS 540, EP2: 289–99), while divisions into 28 and 66 classes are detailed in various passages of his December 1908 letters and manuscripts (L463: 132–46, 150; EP2: 478–91; Lieb 1977: 80–85). Common to all these classifications are the categories of firstness, secondness, and thirdness, which constitute the basis for Peirce’s conception of a triadic sign — a relation between sign, object, and interpretant — as well as the (triple) modalities derived from his trichotomies (or the aspects by which a sign can be described or analyzed) (Houser, 1991). All these classifications are subject to the “qualification rule” (Savan, 1988: 14), which guarantees the logical coherence of the possible classes of signs, ruling out, for instance, classes formed of firsts determined by anything other than other firsts. The combination of these principles results in specific numbers of classes, depending on how many trichotomies are considered in a classification: 3 classes if only one trichotomy is considered (as in the case of icon, index, and symbol, which represent three modalities of the relation between the sign and its direct object); 10 classes if three trichotomies are taken into account; 28 if six trichotomies are considered; and 66 if ten trichotomies are included.

Identifying the semiotic triad and the categories of firstness, secondness and thirdness in problem solving allows us to apply Peirce's model of 10 classes of signs to problem solving. The objective of doing that is to unveil the complex structure of constraints involved in solving a problem. The 10 classes of signs are derived from three trichotomies. Each trichotomy breaks down a component of the semiotic triad (sign, object and interpretant), into their phaneroscopic elements of firstness, secondness and thirdness (Table 1).

	1st trichotomy	2nd trichotomy	3rd trichotomy
Monadic relation (S-dependent)	QUALISIGN in itself, the sign is of the nature of an appearance (EP 2: 291)	ICON a sign which refers to the object merely by virtue of characters of its own (CP 2.247)	RHEME a sign which, for its interpretant, is a sign of possibility
Dyadic relation (S-O dependent)	SINSIGN in itself, the sign is of the nature of an individual object or fact (EP 2: 291)	INDEX a sign which refers to the object by virtue of some existential relation	DICENT a sign which, for its interpretant, is a sign of actual existence (EP 2: 292)
Triadic relation (S-O-I dependent)	LEGISIGN in itself, the sign is of the nature of a general type (CP 8.334)	SYMBOL a sign which refers to the object by virtue of some law	ARGUMENT a sign which, for its interpretant, is a sign of law (CP 2.252)

Table 1: Three trichotomies and three kinds of relations (CP 2.243).

The first trichotomy describes the morphological variety of the sign, or representamen. It answers the question: What is the relation of the sign to itself? This relation may be genuinely triadic, having the nature of a law (legisign). Alternatively, it may be degenerate to the first degree, having the nature of a reaction (sinsign), a dyadic relation. Finally, it may be degenerate to the second degree, having the nature of a feeling (qualisign), a monadic relation. The second trichotomy, considered the "most fundamental classification of signs" (CP 2.275), describes the variety of the object in its relation to the sign. It answers the question: What is the relation between the sign and its object? If the relation is monadic—a triadic relation degenerate to the second degree—it has the nature of a feeling or quality (icon). Conversely, the sign may relate to its object dyadically—a triadic relation degenerate to the first degree—with the nature of a reaction (index). Finally, the sign may relate to its object in a genuinely triadic way, having the nature of a general law, where S is related to O only through I (symbol). The third trichotomy describes the morphological variety of interpretants in their triadic relation to the sign and object. When the interpretant relation has the nature of a qualitative feeling, a monadic relation, it is a rheme: "a sign which, for its interpretant, is a sign of qualitative possibility, that is, is understood as representing such and such a kind of possible object" (CP 2.250). When the interpretant relation has the nature of a reaction, a dyadic relation, it is a dicent sign or dicisign. Finally, the interpretant relation may also be genuinely triadic, having the nature of a law or habit. In this case, it is an argument: "a sign which, for its interpretant, is a sign of law" (CP 2.252).

How many classes are there? If we combine the three possibilities for each of the three trichotomies, we arrive at 27 classes of signs ($3 \times 3 \times 3$). However, hierarchical constraints preclude most of these combinations. The trichotomous divisions are structured according to an order of assumption associated with the categories: the character of sign presentation (firstness), the character of sign representation (secondness), and the interpretive power of the sign (thirdness).

The cross-relations that satisfy the constraints, or the 10 classes of signs, are (EP 2:294-296; CP 2.254-263) (Figure 1):

Figure 1. The 10 classes of signs as a system of cross-relational classes. The paths correspond to the possible compounds of relations (figure based on Merrell, 1996: 8).

In problem-solving, this means breaking down the artifact (first trichotomy), the problem (second trichotomy), and the solution (third trichotomy) into a complex structure of interactions between qualities, reactions, and habits (see Table 2). Following the premises of process philosophy (see Rescher, 1996), artifact, problem, and solution here should all be understood as processes. Considered together, the three trichotomies express how artifact, problem, and solution constrain, synchronically and diachronically, each step of problem solving.

1st trichotomy	sign (S)	artifact	3 - habitual artifacts (legisign) 2 - existent artifacts (sinsign) 1 - artifact qualities (qualisign)
2nd trichotomy	object (S-O)	problem	3 - habitual problem (symbol) 2 - reactive problem (index) 1 - qualitative problem (icon)
3rd trichotomy	interpretant (S-O-I)	solution	3 - habitualization (argument) 2 - search (dicent) 1 - framing (rheme)

Table 2: The first trichotomy models the artifact, the second the problem, and the third the problem solution.

Let's start with the first trichotomy. During problem solving, the agent manipulates artifacts in a task environment. However, different aspects or natures make up an artifact, and which

the agent may interact with at different stages. On the level of firstness, the agent manipulates a set of material and sensorial qualities embodied in the artifact (shapes, colors, sounds, phonemes, relations, parallelisms, textures, etc). This is the artifact as a qualisign. On the level of secondness, the agent manipulates the artifact as a token, a singular existent in its specific situated environment (“this piece on the board”, “this line on the map”, “this pattern of rhyme”...). This is the artifact as a sinsign. On the level of thirdness, the agent interacts with the artifact as a set of distributed and general habits, a type (a kind of puzzle-game, a kind of map, regardless of the specificities of this or that token). The artifact here is a general entity composed of a set of regularities. This is the artifact as a legisign. In short, we interpret qualisigns as artifact properties, sinsigns as reactive (existent) artifacts, and legisigns as habitual artifacts. In problem solving, these different levels of artifactuality constrain the solving activity in different ways.

Through the manipulation of the artifact, the agent engages with a problem. The second trichotomy (icon, index, symbol) helps to clarify the nature of this engagement. On the level of firstness, the problem is tentatively defined by the artifact, without a very clear indication of how exactly the states of the artifact correspond or not to states of the problem. At this level, the problem has the character of an icon, something that only possibly exists, but whose actual modes of operation haven't been discovered or defined. We call it a *qualitative problem*, a problem only qualitatively defined or framed. For example, we can approach urban navigation in terms of a geographically accurate map, which is one kind of artifact, or in terms of a diagram of relations like an electrical circuit diagram, which is another kind of artifact (for example, the subway map),⁵ and these are two different ways of iconically framing the problem of urban navigation. These different frames alter the space of possibilities on which the solution may be developed.

On the level of secondness, the problem is experienced as a set of hard, external constraints that compel the artifact. Here, problem states are not automatically embodied in the artifact, but rather mapped onto it, imposing restrictions on its properties. Following Peircean vocabulary, we can say that the problem is *reactive*, which is to say that it is actually available through the artifact by forcing this artifact to behave in some way. For example, a certain underground diagram is forced to display a certain structure of connection of stations and lines because that's how they are really connected in the city, regardless of whether this is convenient or not for the artifact. Here, the artifact does not determine the problem, but rather the problem determines the artifact. This is the problem as an indexical referent. Note that a reactive problem requires an actual, existent artifact (sinsign). On the level of thirdness, the problem is experienced as a general pattern, distributed across different possible representations. When we say “the problem of urban navigation”, we are referring to such a pattern, a habit generalized from many instances of specific problem-solving processes. This is the problem as symbolically defined. In short, we consider icons as qualitative problems, indices as reactive problems, and symbols as habitual problems. In problem-solving, these are different levels of a problem, all of which interact and influence problem-solving.

⁵ In the paper “Iconic semiosis and representational efficiency in the London Underground Diagram (LUD)”, we analyze the LUD’s efficiency through diverse theories of iconicity (Ata, Bitarello & Queiroz, 2014). We argue that specialized representations, like the LUD, act as icons of their problem’s formal structure — embedding rules of action and behavior to distribute cognitive effort and shape problem-solving niches.

The third trichotomy describes the interaction or engagement of the agent with the problem through the artifact. This is what we identified as the solution process. On the level of firstness, the solution process amounts to tentatively framing a problem through an artifact, which can just offer hypothetical possibilities of solution. This is a rhematic level of problem solving. On the level of secondness, the solution process amounts to a mapping and searching in a problem through the artifact. Search differs from mere framing in that it has a target, typically a solution-state. In this mode of engagement, the agent explores the problem space in a targeted way, for example, by comparing actual problem states, as signified by the artifact, to a goal state. This is a dicentric level of problem solving. On the level of thirdness, beyond searching for a solution state, the process consists in habitualizing the solution at hand — figuring out how a problem is constituted, how a solution works, and under which circumstances it will continue to work. This is an argumentative level of problem solving. In short, we consider rhemes as framing, dicents as searching for a problem, and arguments as habitualizing a problem-solving process.

The three trichotomies, combined, form 10 classes of signs, instead of 27 ($3 \times 3 \times 3$), due to how the hierarchical ordering of the trichotomies preclude most of the classes generated by trichotomic combination. For instance, artifact qualities can only stand to a qualitative problem — and not for a reactive or a habitual problem — for an operation of framing — and not for searching or for habitualization. The ten classes of signs described in problem solving are shown in Table 3 below:

333	Artifact habits, habitual problem and solution (habitualizing).
332	Artifact habits, habitual problem and reactive solution (searching).
331	Artifact habits, habitual problem and qualitative solution (framing).
322	Artifact habits, reactive problem and reactive solution (searching).
321	Artifact habits, reactive problem and qualitative solution (framing).
311	Artifact habits, qualitative problem and qualitative solution (framing).
222	Artifact reactions, reactive problem and solution (searching).
221	Artifact reactions, reactive problem and qualitative solution (framing).
211	Artifact reactions, qualitative problem and solution (framing).
111	Artifact qualities, qualitative problem and solution (framing).

Table 3: 10 sign classes interpreted as problem solving process.

In short, there are three semiotic components in problem solving — artifact, problem, and solution — and three kinds of constraints that each of these components can exert on problem solving — qualitative, reactive, and habitual. Put together, they determine three trichotomies and 10 classes of signs in problem solving. The categories model the different ways in which artifact, problem and solution constrain problem solving. In the next section, we explore the interrelation between the 10 classes, to arrive at a full picture of how the different constraints interact together to constitute problem-solving activities.

4. Relations between 10 classes: Ballat's diagram

During the 1980s, a group of semioticians from the University of Perpignan focused their efforts on studying the structures and relations present in Peirce's extended classifications of signs (10, 28, 66 classes of signs).⁶ As a result, one of the participants of this group, Michel Balat, proposed three diagrams for the 10 classes of signs: a triangular diagram (Balat, 1990: 81, Figure 2), a square diagram (Balat, 1990: 85), and a three-dimensional diagram (Balat, 1990: 86). We will focus on one of them — the triangular diagram (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Balat's triangular diagram for Peirce's 10 classes of signs (adapted from Balat, 1990: 81).

The diagram shows the relationships (arrows) connecting each of the 10 sign classes. There are two kinds of arrows: pointing up and down. They correspond to two types of relationships that reduce all others: "involvement relationships" ($2 > 1$) and "instantiation relationships" ($3 > 2$). This generalization is based on two types of relationships — token $>$ tone, $2 > 1$; type $>$ token, $3 > 2$ — and, in turn, are based on the relationships between the categories (CP 1.528, 5.49, 5.91) and describe how "generals" (types) "instantiate" an indeterminate number of "singulars" (tokens), or existents, and prescribe their qualities (tone): "involvement" (secondness $>$ firstness, $2 > 1$), "instantiation" (thirdness $>$ secondness, $3 > 2$). Peirce asserted that 'laws' only become real through their instantiation in actual existents. Their reality is tied to the regularities we observe in nature. Simply put, laws don't exist on their own in some Platonic ideal; they only have being when realized in the concrete world (see Savan 1987-88: 13). While laws are instantiated (existents), existents involve qualities. The diagram (figure 2) represents relations of involvement and instantiation between signs of decreasing generality, from right to left. Every arrow pointing down represents instantiation, and every arrow pointing up represents involvement. Thus, arguments (333) instantiate propositions (332) that involve rhematic symbols (terms, 331) to constitute the predicate of the proposition and dicent indexical legisigns (322) to "indicate" its subject. Legisigns instantiate sinsigns, and so on down to the qualisign (111). Table 4, below, specifies each relation of instantiation and involvement shown on the diagram.

⁶ The main members of this group, under the influence and coordination of Gerard Delleale, were: Joelle Rethore, Antony Jappy, Robert Marty, and Michel Balat.

relation of instantiation	relation of involvement
(333 – 332) Argument-Dicent instantiation; habitual solution instantiated in reactive solution; instantiation of habitual solution.	(332 – 331) Dicent-Rheme involvement; reactive solution involves a qualitative solution; involvement of a framing.
(332 – 322) Symbol-Index instantiation; habitual problem instantiated in reactive problem; instantiation of habitual problem (when searching)	(322 – 321) Dicent-Rheme involvement; reactive solution involves qualitative solution; involvement of a framing (problem reactions to artifact habits)
(331 – 321) Symbol-index instantiation; habitual problem instantiated in reactive problem; instantiation of habitual problem (when framing)	(222 – 221) Dicent-Rheme involvement; reactive solution involves qualitative solution; involvement of a framing (problem reactions to artifact actions)
(322 – 222) Legisign-Sinsign instantiation; artifact habits are instantiated by artifact actions; instantiation of artifact habits (when searching a reactive problem)	(321 – 311) Index-Icon involvement; reactive problem involves qualitative problem; involvement of qualitative problem (by artifact habits)
(321 – 221) Legisign-Sinsign instantiation; artifact habits instantiated by artifact actions; instantiation of artifact habits (when framing a reactive problem)	(221 – 211) Index-Icon involvement; reactive problem involves qualitative problem; involvement of qualitative problems (by artifact actions)
(311 – 211) Legisign-Sinsign instantiation; artifact habits instantiated by artifact actions; instantiation of artifact habits (when framing a qualitative problem)	(211 – 111) Sinsign-Qualisign involvement; artifact reactions involve artifact qualities; involvement of artifact qualities

Table 4: Description of all the relationships of involvement and instantiation between each of the 10 classes of signs, as shown in Ballat's diagram.

If we try to locate each of the trichotomies, which we discussed in the previous section, in Ballat's diagram, we arrive at the results shown in Figures 2, 3, and 4 below. The figures show how the properties of being habitual, reactive, or qualitative are distributed, which are attributed to solutions, problems, and artifacts, and are distributed across a phenomenological space of semiotic relations. Figure 3 shows how artifact habits are ultimately instantiated by artifact reactions, which in turn ultimately involve artifact qualities. Figure 4 shows how symbols are instantiated by indices that involve icons. Figure 5 shows how habitualization is instantiated by searching, which involves framing.

Figure 3: Ballat's diagram segmented according to the first trichotomy (artifacts). Area A corresponds to qualitative artifacts (qualisigns); area B corresponds to reactive artifacts (sinsigns); area C corresponds to habitual artifacts (legisigns)

Figure 4: Ballat's diagram segmented according to the second trichotomy (problems). Area A corresponds to qualitative problems (icons); area B corresponds to reactive problems (indices); area C corresponds to habitual problems (symbols)

Figure 5: Ballat's diagram segmented according to the third trichotomy (solutions). Area A corresponds to qualitative solution, or framing (rhemes); area B corresponds to reactive solution, or searching (dicents); area C corresponds to habitual problems, or habitualization (arguments)

We will use Ballat's diagram here to model the synchronic constraints acting in problem solving. The diagram represents the complex structure of presuppositions and determinations between artifact, problem and solution in problem solving. Each node in the diagram — each sign class — is a configuration of qualitative, reactive, and/or habitual constraints exerted by the artifact, the problem, and the solution. The arrows represent a hierarchy of containment and presupposition, so that 333 (the rightmost node, which represents a fully habitualized problem-solving process) presupposes and contains all the other nodes, while 111 (the leftmost node, which represents a fully qualitative problem-solving process) does not presuppose nor contain any other. How does the diagram represent a process of problem-solving? Let's consider two possible ways of reading the diagram as a representation of problem solving — the mereology of problem solving and the temporal succession of actions in problem solving.

First let's consider a mereological approach to understand how the diagram represents a problem-solving process. From this perspective, the sign class of arguments (333), represents a complete process of solving a problem, which can roughly be defined as finding a stable and habitual structure of constraints between artifact, problem, and solution. We can then read the diagram from right to left as a mereological structure of problem-solving. Starting from node 333, at the rightmost and topmost vertex of the triangular diagram, and moving left and down following the direction of the arrows, at each successive step, we decompose this whole process of problem solving into its logical components.

Each habitual constraint (habitual artifact, problem, and solution), or each number 3 in the diagram, needs to be instantiated, rightwards and downwards in the diagram by a number of component reactive constraints (numbers 2). This is represented by all the arrows pointing down. Thus, habitual solutions (in 333) are instantiated by solution steps (in 332, 322, 222); habitual problems (in 331 and 332) are instantiated by reactive problems (in 321 and 322) and habitual artifacts (in 331, 321 and 311) need to be instantiated by reactive artifacts (in 211, 221 and 222). There is a hierarchical order in these chains of instantiations: habitual solutions require habitual problems and habitual problems require habitual artifacts, in this

order. Note that the class 333 is ultimately instantiated by all others. In turn, each reactive constraint (reactive artifact, problem, and solution) necessarily involves a number of component qualitative constraints. Thus, reactive solutions (in 332, 322 and 222) involve qualitative solutions (in 331, 321, 221, 311, 211 and 111); reactive problems (in 322, 321, 222 and 221) involve qualitative problems (in 311, 211 and 111); and reactive artifacts (in 222, 221 and 211) involve qualitative artifacts (in 111). Here again, there is a hierarchical ordering of relations: a reactive solution already presupposes a reactive problem, and this in turn presupposes a reactive artifact. Note that class 111 is ultimately involved in all others.

Let's now consider the time of problem-solving processes. The diagram does not accurately represent the temporal development of problem solving because each level of sign action has a different phaneroscopic temporality — thirdness, the category of habits, is the level where phaneroscopic time is historical and cumulative, made of generalized patterns; secondness, the category of reaction, is the level where phaneroscopic time is successive and concrete, made of actual events; firstness, the category of qualities of feeling, is the level where phaneroscopic time is made of a vague and undefined present.

When we think of the successive steps or actions that an agent takes in a problem-solving task, we are talking about the time of secondness. If we look at the diagram, this time of successive reactive events is reflected in class 222, which is the node at the bottom of the triangle diagram. Thus, if we want to grasp how the structure of constraints represented in the diagram acts in each successive step in problem solving, we can focus on the class of dicent indexical sinsigns (222). In this case, the process of solving a problem can be understood as a temporal succession of dicent indexical sinsigns. Each of these actions taken by an agent, is subject to qualitative, reactive and habitual constraints stemming from the artifact, problem, and solution, and this is what the diagram models.

If we move left from 222, we examine the qualitative aspects involved in each action taken in a problem-solving task. These qualitative aspects provide initiating conditions for the focal action emerging at 222. A reactive solution (as in 222) involves and presupposes a reactive problem (as in 221, a rhematic indexical sinsign), but this in turn involves and presupposes a reactive artifact (as in 211, an iconic sinsign). Or, reading it the other way around, a qualitative artifact (111, a qualisign) provides the initiating conditions for a reactive artifact (211, an iconic sinsign), and this for a reactive problem (221, a rhematic indexical sinsign) and this in turn for a reactive solution (222, dicent indexical sinsign), which is an action taken, and we are back to the point where we began.

If we move right from 222, we examine the habits involved in each action taken in a problem-solving task. Each reactive step in problem solving instantiates habits. These habits are a constraining factor that participates in selecting, out of many possible actions, that which is actually taken. There are three of these boundary constraints, in successive order: the constraint from habitual artifacts, from habitual problems, and from habitual solutions. Thus, each 222 instantiates, first, the habits of the artifact being used, then the habits of the problem being approached through the artifact, and then the habits of the solution being developed.

5. Conclusion and implications

One of the implications of our approach — problem-solving based on the ten classes of signs — is that we distinguish three distinct levels involved in the problem-solving activity: S

(firstness), S-O (secondness), and S-O-I (thirdness). Traditional problem-solving models are unidimensional and tend to propose phases or stages such as framing and searching. In contrast, we do not treat problem-solving as a succession of phases or stages but as a hierarchical interaction. At the firstness level (S), problem-solving concerns the nature of artifacts themselves, focusing on their inherent qualities and characteristics. At the secondness level (S-O), it involves exploring the relationship between these artifacts and the problems they embody, examining how they interact and affect one another. At the thirdness level (S-O-I), problem-solving is about interpreting this relationship between artifacts and problems, deriving meaning and understanding that guide the resolution process. By viewing problem-solving as an interaction across these hierarchical levels, we move beyond the linear progression of traditional models. This perspective allows for a more nuanced understanding of how artifacts, their relationships to problems, and the interpretation of these relationships all contribute integrally to the problem-solving process.

Our approach can be seen as a synchronic functional anatomy of constraints, based on ten classes of signs — complex semiotic processes within complex processes that are both synchronic and interdependent. We argue that thinking in temporal terms, or relying on a linear conception of time that prioritizes successive states as phases, is misguided. The 333 class, continuously produced and requiring constant reproduction, is a product in process. A common pitfall is the tendency to view classes of signs as distinct entities. However, in our approach, they are synchronous and interdependent processes. The triangular diagram maps degrees of affinity between classes of constraints, illustrating that the relationship between class 321 and class 311 is a process dependent on the relationship between classes 332 and 331. This diagram is not a sequence of steps or temporal successions but a map of constraints, a map of coercions.

Discussions of the temporal development (across many scales) of semiosis appear in the works of numerous authors: the ontogeny of semiosis, the maturation of semiotic processes, the evolution of signs.⁷ For Floyd Merrell, the categories are treated as successive phases in a process of semiotic ontogeny (or semiotic learning), typically moving from the less general to the more general. On the other hand, thinkers like Gérard Deledalle, Michel Balat, and Max Bense approach this in terms of nested hierarchies and containment relationships: arguments contain propositions, and propositions contain propositional terms. These relationships are of presupposition, on the one hand, and instantiation, on the other. They are components of a hierarchical structure, not phases in a linear temporal development. Our description diverges from both tendencies. Here, the central notion is that temporality itself must be understood differently for each of the three categories in their respective logical modalities. What we're dealing with is a dynamic complex system, where each category interacts with time in a distinct manner, embedded in its own logical structure.

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⁷ See: Deacon's *Symbolic Species* (1997); Hoffmeyer in *Biosemiotics* (2008); Petrilli & Ponzio in *Semiotics Unbounded* (2005).

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